

Switzerland

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Switzerland, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the Swiss higher education system includes higher education institutions and tertiary level professional education. Higher education institutions include two types of HEIs:

- **Universities:** There are **ten cantonal universities** and **two federal institutes of technology (FIT)**. The universities in Basel, Bern, Lucerne, St. Gallen and Zurich and the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich (ETHZ) are in the German-speaking part of Switzerland, while the universities of Geneva, Lausanne and Neuchâtel and the École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) are in the French-speaking part of Switzerland. The University of Fribourg is in the bilingual canton of Fribourg (French and German), and the Università della Svizzera italiana in the Italian-speaking canton of Ticino. The Graduate Institute of International and Development Studies (IHEID) in Geneva, and the Swiss Distance University Switzerland are also considered to be university-level institutions. The universities organise their courses of study in a three-year Bachelor degree (full-time study) and a Master programme lasting one-and-a-half to two years (full-time study). They all also award PhD.
- **Universities of applied sciences (UAS):** As of 2020, there were nine (cantonal or intercantonal) universities of applied sciences recognised by the Confederation². These are distributed over eight Swiss regions in multiple locations. The Confederation has also recognised one private university of applied sciences. The universities of applied sciences offer their courses of study as a three-year Bachelor programme (full-time study); the Bachelor degree qualifies graduates for a profession and is the standard qualification. Following the successful completion of the Bachelor programme, students may complete a Master programme lasting one-and-a-half to two years (full-time study).
- The science-based vocational and professional training and professional development of teaching staff and of experts in the field of special education is mainly carried out at **universities of teacher education (UTE)**. The cantons, which are the maintaining bodies for the universities of teacher

¹ <https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/switzerland/types-higher-education-institutions>

² From 1st January 2020, the University of Applied Sciences of Eastern Switzerland was split in two institutions, the Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences and the Grisons University of Applied Sciences.

education, are responsible for their organisation and funding. Some of the UTE are independent institutions, others are integrated as departments within UAS.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 below provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. Cantonal universities (*Kantonale Universitäten*) are all public institutions and have the right to award PhDs. In total, about 27% of all Swiss HEIs are cantonal universities and equivalent institutions. Federal universities of technology (*Eidgenössische Technische Hochschulen*) account for 5% of all Swiss HEIs, both award PhDs. The 14 universities of teacher education (*Pädagogische Hochschulen*) and the nine universities of applied sciences (*Fachhochschulen*) account for the majority of all HEIs in Switzerland but do not award PhDs. The two other university institutions (*Andere Universitäre Institutionen*) play a more limited role, one of them awards PhDs. Only two HEIs in Switzerland are private.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
Cantonal university	Kantonale Universität	10	10	0	10
Federal university of technology	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule	2	2	0	2
Other university institution	Andere Universitäre Institutionen	2	1	1	1
University of applied sciences	Fachhochschule	9	8	1	0
University of teacher education	Pädagogische Hochschule	14	14	0	0
Total		37	35	2	13

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Switzerland's higher education and its evolution over time.

Figure 1 shows that, despite ancient historical roots, the expansion of the system in terms of the number of HEIs is relatively recent. While the University of Basel, the oldest Swiss university, dates to 1460, only 8 HEIs were founded before the 20th century, including 7 cantonal universities and 1 federal university of technology. Overall, however, Swiss HEIs are much younger; only 3 of the HEIs were founded before World War II, nearly two third of the Swiss HEIs were founded after 1992 – reflecting the expansion of the HEI system in terms of

universities of teacher education and universities of applied sciences. Some UAS and UTE had however, ancestors such as engineering schools and pedagogical schools.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Students

In contrast to the number of institutions, in terms of the number of students enrolled, cantonal universities still account for 44% of all students and universities of applied sciences for another 37%. The other institutional types play a relatively minor role in the aggregate (see Figure 2). According to different institutional mandates, we also observe systematic differences between educational levels: Cantonal universities account for 38% of the bachelor students and 55% of the master students, while doctorates and long master's degrees enrolments (without an intermediate bachelor's degree) are exclusive to cantonal universities and federal universities of technology.

In contrast, *Fachhochschulen* account for 46% of the bachelor students but only 19% of the master students. This pattern closely matches the policy intention to focus universities of applied sciences on shorter professional curricula; however, their role has become relevant also in master education.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Total students include ISCED 6-7

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority.

As shown by Figure 3, there are major differences between HEIs in size, as measured by total personnel in full time equivalents (FTE), and in the personnel composition. With an average of nearly 8,000 FTEs, the two federal institutes of technology are the largest HEIs in the country, followed by cantonal universities (average 3,000 FTE) and universities of applied sciences (1,800 FTE). These differences reflect distinct levels of engagement in research and in education. As of the personnel composition, the share of administrative and technical personnel is similar by type of HEIs between 30 and 34%, while there are large variations in the share of research and teaching assistants (RTAs). This category is mostly composed by PhD and master students supporting research and teaching activities; RTAs comprise 39% of personnel in the federal institutes of technology and 26% in cantonal universities, but only 11% in universities of applied sciences and 4% in university of teacher education, reflecting the different extent of research and the fact that the latter institutions cannot award PhDs.

Figure 3. Personnel (FTE) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Since the data collection 2020, ETER also includes information on academic staff seniority level based on a classification jointly developed by OECD and EUROSTAT³. Combined with information on gender, this information allows measuring two critical issues, i.e. career prospects of academic staff and the so-called leaky pipeline, i.e. the fact that the share of female academic staff decreases systematically with seniority levels.

As of Switzerland, data are available only for the two federal universities of technology, cantonal universities and other university institution (see Figure 4) and show a very steep hierarchy, with 44% of academic personnel at the junior level and only 11% at the senior level; a reasonable gender balance has been achieved for junior personnel, but only 21% of senior-level academic personnel are female (see Figure 4).

³ OECD (2022), Education at a Glance, Paris, pp. 412-413.

Figure 4. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender (HC), 2020

Note: Only federal universities of technology, cantonal universities and other university institutions included

A final important dimension is internationality since it is generally considered as beneficial for the quality of research and education. In ETER, this is measured by the share of academic personnel not having the citizenship of the country ('foreigners'). As shown by Figure 5, Swiss higher education is characterized by a high level of internationality with more than 40% of foreign academic personnel. In federal universities of technology, over 70% of academic personnel are foreign and almost half in cantonal universities, while this share drops to one-quarter in universities of applied sciences and to one-tenth in university of teacher education. Internationality is therefore strongly associated with research orientation of HEIs. A slow increase over the last ten years can also be observed.

Figure 5. Share of foreign academic personnel (HC) by type of HEI, 2011 and 2020

Note: 2020 data are not fully comparable to previous years due to change in definitions

Financial resources

As illustrated in Figure 6, in the year 2020 the cantonal universities accounted for 48% of financial revenues, and 44% of academic personnel of the whole HEI system, which equals more or less than the share of students. On the other side, the two federal universities of technology account for more than 23% of financial revenues of the public HEI system and 17% of academic personnel of the whole HEI system, i.e. substantially more than their share of students (11%). In turn, the universities of applied sciences serve with one quarter of the overall financial revenues for 38% of the students. These differences mainly reflect varying levels of engagement in research.

This difference is also reflected in the composition of revenues (see Figure 7), where cantonal universities and federal universities of technology receive a substantial proportion of revenues from (research-related) third-party funds. Overall, state allocation remains dominant for all institutional types in Switzerland, while student fees play a minor role and are only relevant for universities of applied sciences (11%).

Figure 6. Resources, academic personnel and total students enrolled by type of HEI, 2020

Figure 7. Composition of resources by type of HEI, 2020

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students (Figure 8), data show a pattern of steady increase with the number of enrolled students increasing by 27% from 2011 to 2020. While the number of students of cantonal universities grew by 16% from 2011 to 2020, federal institutes of technologies (+41%), universities of teacher education (+41%) and universities of applied Sciences (+34%) show an above average increase of students. Overall, the observed pattern over the considered period is of moderate expansion within the observed institutional structure.

Figure 8. Students enrolled by type of HEI, 2011-2020

As shown by Figure 9, with an increase of 25% from 2011 to 2020, the number of academic personnel (FTE) in Swiss HEIs kept pace with the increase in the number of students. Like for students, the increase of academic personnel was stronger in federal universities of technology (+28%) and in universities of applied sciences (+33%) than in cantonal universities (+18%).

Figure 9. Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2011-2020

Note: To keep consistency, the figure includes teaching and research assistants since these were included in academic personnel until 2019.

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